

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

THE STUDY RESULTS ON THE USE OF BLUE AND GREEN INFRASTRUCTURES BY THE POPULATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA

Galstyan M.H. ,

Armenian National Agrarian University, Doctor of Science, Researcher

Sayadyan H. Ya. ,

*Faculty of Geography and Geology, Yerevan State University,
Doctor of Science, Researcher*

Sargsyan K.Sh.,

Armenian National Agrarian University, Candidate of Science, Researcher

Hoveyan Z. H.

Armenian National Agrarian University, Researcher

Abstract

The blue and green infrastructures (BGI) are vitally important elements of urban environment. In the Republic of Armenia (RA), where about 67% of population is located in 57 towns the significance of proper BGI is crucial. It is also important to promote comfortable living environment in cities, where dry continental climate with hot summer and cold winter prevails. This specific research, based on both on-line survey and face to face interviews and mapping, is designed to understand the perception, preferences and use of BGI by the urban population of the Republic of Armenia (RA). Overall per capita green spaces of general uses are insufficient both in capital Yerevan, Vanadzor city, where on-line survey and interviews were performed, as well as in other urban areas. According to the study, the majority of urban population prefers large and small parks, as well as forests and lakes. Most responders in Yerevan prefer Yerevan Kentron (Centre) district, especially circular park, due to the variety of services. The low percent of facilities demonstrates the necessity of green areas with various infrastructure. The population generally evaluated the quality, accessibility and availability of the areas as on-satisfactory. The distance from the house to the preferred recreation area in most cases exceeds the access road on foot (up to 9-10 km), which is a serious challenge from the point of view of transport security. This study, along with similar research works, will enable effective management of blue and green infrastructures in urban areas.

Keywords: Blue and green infrastructures (BGI), urbanization, on-line survey, face to face interview, respondents, preferences, accessibility and availability of green areas, quality of green areas

Introduction.

The literature on BGI studies and its different aspects, specifically for the Eastern Europe and particularly on Caucasus region are not many. Few studies are covering different aspects of urban BGI for Eastern Europe region from the point of view to their availability, accessibility and quality of urban greenspace [1]; urban densification, which are very similar to those in Europe's West [2] and globally; human perceptions of and preferences for urban green spaces in diverse contexts [3; 4; 5]; the frequencies and types of urban greenspace usage [3; 6; 7].

Urban development in the RA took place mostly in XX century. The general plan of Yerevan city and green landscapes was developed by famous Armenian architect Alexander Tamanyan in 1924. Tamanyan succeeded to introduce 3-square concept and major elements of garden-cities, e.g. 3 green belts, circular and radial avenues/large streets, extended green landscapes. His principal ideas of Yerevan city plan, including green landscapes were widely applied in the 1939, 1951, 1971 and 2008 years planning [8].

The large-scale and goal-oriented greening of Yerevan city was started in 1940-50s. In 1955 all green zones in Yerevan had 1500 ha area. Starting from 1953 plantings of green zones became dense, canopies were closed and needs of thinning became evident. It was

started the major period of establishment of parks, plantings, streets' greening and other functional meaning green zones. For the city greening were used about 200 trees and bush species [9]. Trees and bushes of Yerevan city green circle, 1985). In the middle of 1960s the total area of green plantings in Yerevan city was about 1900 ha: including 501 ha for general use (provision per capita 7.7 m²/person), 375 ha-for limited use and 1025.7 ha had for special meaning [10].

In the beginning of 1970s, the total area of green plantings constituted already 6858 ha: including 791 ha-for general use, 2135 ha- for limited use and 3931 ha for special meaning. In 1980s the real city greening figures systematically stand behind from the planned ones. The provision of general use green areas sometimes decreased due to quick increase of population: 12.0 m²/person (1983) and 9.69 m²/person (1990). Till 1990s the Yerevan city greening were realized on the base of above-mentioned projects, but gradually the gap between planned and real planted green areas was increasing. In 1990s the perspective greening draft, in general, was realized by 42% from the point of view per capita provision [11; 12]. It is evident that in 1990-2003 the area of general use and special meaning green zones have decreased essentially. In this period summary lost of green areas' surface constituted 1216.6 ha,

and in general balance (thanks to limited use green areas' increasing) 660.5 ha. Mostly were damaged general use and special meaning green areas accordingly by 42% and 36.3% [13].

According to the official statement of Yerevan municipality [14] the green areas in Yerevan city currently compose 6760 ha (about 30% of city total area- 223 km²) that includes general and limited used green areas, as well as all green vegetation covered areas, including flowerbeds and lawns. Yerevan has 86 parks of city significance. The general use green area is 869 ha, which provided about 7,8 m² green space per habitant.

The significance of public-use blue and aquatic areas, as well as green plantations in the urban environment is exponentially growing parallel to the development of cities [15, 16]. Similar areas in the cities have multifunctional roles and can serve as a sound background for the establishment of recreational, sanitary and hygienic, aesthetic, psycho-semantic and favorable microclimatic conditions [15]. The ecological and biological researches have indicated that safeguarding the required natural medium for the human life activity in the urbanized areas is possible only via conservation of green spaces and intensive treatment of plants covering those areas [17; 18].

For the development of the contemporary society, a special attention should be paid to the ecological component, since it is often affected by the deterioration of human living environment. The issue related to the ecological state of the cities is of particular urgency, since they contain complicated, distinguished social and economic systems with high anthropogenic impact on nature [19]. The green areas emit phytoncides, which have bactericidal properties, in addition, they also kill pathogens dangerous for human health, along with regulating the temperature and relative air humidity, saturating air with oxygen and simultaneously imbibing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere [20; 21; 22].

Hence, the establishment of appropriate ecological and economic mechanisms for the management of blue and green spaces of urban habitat in line with the contemporary development requirements, analysis of the challenges concerning the civil participation and public control, particularly, those related to the management of recreational zones, as well as the analysis of the opinion of civil society and evaluation of the consecutive results is ultimately vital and relevant. The implementation of the measures based on those analyses will ensure the expansion of blue-green spaces of a specific city or residence, the increase of their functional efficiency, as well as population's refreshment, healthy lifestyle, rejuvenation and prolongation of human life expectancy.

Materials and methods

In cooperation with the National Agricultural Universities of Ukraine (Kyiv, Lviv) and Agricultural University of Georgia and through the financial support of Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, the Armenian National Agrarian University (ANAU) has implemented the "Blue-Green Urban Infrastructures in Europe's West and East" project, within the framework of transnational partnership towards the academic integration in Europe. The project aims to disclose and evaluate the sanitary and hygienic conditions of recreational areas, forest park spaces, reservoirs, resorts in that specific country, to figure out frequency and opportunities of people's visits to those places, as well as to identify the factors and trends which could make the mentioned places more attractive and available for people, in other words to increase their efficiency.

To achieve the mentioned goal, upon the comprehensive analyses and discussions held with the scientific researchers of partner universities engaged in the mentioned program, questionnaires have been compiled and online surveys have been conducted. Based on the provided answers the concerns and recommendations made by the respondents on the blue-green areas have been grouped and evaluated. Besides, events system has been developed, the implementation of which would possibly promote the efficient use of those areas and improvement of human's life quality.

Results and discussions

The results of the conducted in the Republic of Armenia (RA) on-line interviews have indicated that 1167 respondents have answered various questions involved in the questionnaire and they expressed different approaches and views about the way of organizing their rest time. It is worth mentioning that the respondents had the opportunity to give more than one answer to some questions as a result of which the total number of answers can surpass the number of respondents.

The preferences of people for having rest in the changed blue and green areas are different in various natural environments; 72 % of the respondents preferred large parks, 46 % - small parks and 42 % forest areas. It is noteworthy that 42 % of the respondents expressed desire to have playgrounds in the recreation zones and 37 % of them demanded that they should be equipped with the necessary sport facilities. Meanwhile, via the online surveys, it has been revealed that the majority of people extended wish to spend their leisure time at the sea (12 %), lake (42 %), river (30 %) and at the seaside (2.0%). The figure 1 demonstrates how that relatively low percent of the respondents preferred visiting reserves (13 %), lawns (15 %) or church yards/cemeteries (13 %) during their rest time.

Figure 1. What type(s) of nature and green areas in and around your town do you like to use?

Only the results of surveys conducted in the city of Yerevan are slightly different (Figure 2). Most of the respondents prefer to visit a small park (80%), 68% prefer large parks, and 33% prefer a place with a lake.

Figure 2 What type(s) of nature and green areas in Yerevan do you like to use?

The survey results concerning the visits to parks and recreational zones, indicate that the highest percentage of the respondents prefer walking to promenades on foot (62 %) and 51 % - with children (Figure 3). The diagram of the same figure testifies that 36-38 % of the respondents or 421-445 people want to actively spend their leisure time with their friends and family members for the most cases by organizing picnics, meanwhile enjoying natural landscapes, taking photos of picturesque views, as well as via outdoor

games. 23 % of the respondents prefer going to the recreational areas with dogs, 19 % - by bicycle. It is worth mentioning that only 16-17 % of the respondents expressed willingness to get acquainted and study wildlife and enjoy its benefits, like picking up berries and mushrooms, while 9 % expressed a wish for going fishing. Only 11.5 % of the respondents desire to see recreational areas equipped with sport facilities and 5 % want to have opportunity for going in for winter sports.

Figure 3. What do you mostly use nature and green areas in and around your town for?

Researches were also carried out in the city of Yerevan, through face-to-face surveys. 88% of the residents of Yerevan prefer to hold social gatherings in green spaces. 43% of respondents prefer jogging in green or blue areas, and 40% prefer reading (figure 4).

Most responders in Yerevan prefer Yerevan Kentron (Centre) district, especially circular park, due to the variety of services. The low percent of facilities demonstrates the necessity of green areas with various infrastructure.

Figure 4. What do you mostly use nature and green areas in Yerevan for?

The answers and concepts of the respondents referring to accessibility and availability, as well as the quality of the green spaces are of particular interest (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Level of satisfaction by blue and green spaces

The data of figure 5 disclose that 85 people of 1167 respondents or 7.2 % are very much dissatisfied, while 248 people or 21.2 % are dissatisfied with the accessibility of green spaces located within or nearby the cities. Above all these 300 people of the respondents (25.64 %) are satisfied and 30 people or 2.56 % are very satisfied with the opportunities to reach those places, while more than 43.33 % of the total respondents are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied.

At the same time, the data of Figure 5 make it clear that 125 people (10.71 %) among the respondents are very much dissatisfied and 398 people or 34.1% are dissatisfied with the availability of green areas. About 37.45 % or 43 people have given neutral answers, that is, neither dissatisfied nor satisfied. The number of people answering positively, which implies that they are very satisfied with the availability of the discussed sites, is very low, equaling all in all to 9 people, or they make 0.77 % of the respondents, while 198 people or 16.97 % are satisfied with the availability of green-blue areas.

The results of these answers are mainly depending on the distances of green and blue zones from the residences, as well as on the improper operation of public transport. The above mentioned are the circumstances which significantly affect the organization of active leisure. Besides, if we add hereto the people's insufficient socioeconomic conditions, the pollution rate of the mentioned areas and service quality, then we'll get the comprehensive insight into the depicted situation.

The results of the respondents' answers concerning the quality of green and blue areas are also related to the mentioned problems, which are presented in Figure 5. Only 9.38 % of the respondents or 111 people are satisfied and 0.85 % or 10 people are very satisfied with the quality of green spaces located in or around the residential areas. Anyhow, 18.6 % (220 people) are extremely dissatisfied and 448 people or 37.87 % are dissatisfied with the quality of the discussed areas. If we complement the data of dissatisfied people with half of

those people who are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied (neutral), which makes 16.65 % or 197 people, then the amount of dissatisfied and extremely dissatisfied people will amount to 865 people, or 73.93 % of the total respondents.

This circumstance gives rise to serious concerns, since it implies that the green spaces of the settlements are in the ultimately polluted condition, where every inch is littered with plastic bags and various daily/household garbage, which lure down people and become one of the main reasons for the reduction of people's number visiting to those green spaces. This is the main reason why 74.5% of the respondents or about 872 people expressed serious concern about the pollution of the parks and the resulted worse quality.

Conclusions and recommendations

Overall, the analyses on the different aspects of activities in the green areas (recreation, family pastime, sports, social, water events), their quality, accessibility and people's preferences enable to designate the major factors that have rather adverse effect and are obstacles for the development of the BGIs in the cities of RA and particularly in capital Yerevan.

1. Lack of efficient policy for the management and conservation of green areas.
2. Lack of agreed upon consultations and interactive environment and mechanisms between the community authorities, population, specialists of the field and specialized companies.
3. Low engagement of educational institutions, families and population in the caring and maintaining activities of green and water areas and low level of environmentally-friendly behavior and culture.
4. Issuance of construction permits in green areas of public use, ignoring urban planning norms.
5. Deterioration of the overall ecological situation in the cities, which affect the state of green plantations.
6. Lack of regular care and control measures for plant disease prevention in green areas; implementing

pruning with untimely manners and violated frequency of agrotechnical measures and other treatment activities, lack of professional approach, organizational shortcomings.

7. Destruction of green plantations through unjustified "tree-threats" deforestation.

8. Lack of compensatory or mutually complementary landscaping in the areas of cut or withered trees.

9. Insufficient budget funds and its inappropriate use, lack of interest in landscapers for high quality work.

10. During the past 30 years, due to three Artsakh-Azerbaijani wars, as well as the economic difficulties in the cities of Armenia, the energy crisis and blockade of the republic, large-scale logging was implemented in the public-use green areas, which sharply worsened the condition of green plantations in suburban areas both from the qualitative and quantitative standpoints. During the mentioned period, both for the mentioned reasons and in the conditions of the epidemic that started and continued in 2019 (Coronavirus, Omicron), the invested funds, which were aimed at the organization, operation and maintenance of green areas, significantly decreased.

References

1. Hirt, S. 2013. Whatever happened to the (post)socialist city? *Cities* 32:S29-S38.
2. Hirt, S. (2015). *The Rules of Residential Segregation: US Housing Taxonomies and Their Precedents. Planning Perspectives* 30 (3), pp. 167-195.
3. Elbakidze M. et al. Multiple factors shape the interaction of people with urban greenspace: Sweden as a case study. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 74(6):127672.
4. Ugolini F., et al. Effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the use and perceptions of urban green space: An international exploratory study. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, Volume 56, 2020.
5. De la Barrera F., Reyes-Paecke S., Bانشaf E. Indicators for green spaces in contrasting urban settings. *Ecological indicators. Volume 62*, 2016, pp.212-219.
6. Schipperijin J., Ekholm O., Stigsdotter U., Toftager M., Bentsen P., Kamper-Jorgensen F., Randrup Th. Factors influencing the use of green space: Results from a Danish national representative survey. *Landscape and Urban Planning. Volume 95, Issue 3*, 2010, pp.130-137.
7. Madureira, H.; Nunes, F.; Oliveira, J.V.; Madureira, T. Preferences for Urban Green Space Characteristics: A Comparative Study in Three Portuguese Cities. *Environments* 2018, 5, 23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments5020023>
8. Petrosyan A. 2009. "Northern Prospect- observations on Al.Tamanyan's urban development observations". P.24 Inégale: blog.samyzdat: North avenue / Vues Al. Plans de développement urbain de Tamanyan / (pinterest.com)) (In Armenian).
9. Bозoyan A.A. 1985. Trees and bushes of Yerevan city green circle. *Bulletin of Botanical Garden of National Academy of Armenian SSR*, pp.49-57. Деревья и кустарники зеленого кольца Еревана - Pan-Armenian Digital Library (sci.am) (In Russian).
10. Kazaryan V.O., Harutyunyan L.V., Khurshudyan P.A, Grigoryan A.A. and Barseghyan A.M. 1974. The scientific bases of afforestation and greening (landscaping)of Armenian SSR. *Publication of National Academy of Armenian SSR, Yerevan-347 p.* (In Russian).
11. Knuth L. 2006. Greening cities for improving urban livelihoods: Legal, policy and institutional aspects of urban and peri-urban forestry in West and Central Asia (With a case study of Armenia). *FAO, LSP Working paper 37, Access to Natural Resources Subprograms. p.70 Greening cities for improving urban livelihoods: (fao.org).*
12. Sargsyan K. Sh.2005. About the history of the establishment of green zone in Yerevan. *Bulletin of State agrarian university of Armenia. No6*, pp.31-35. (In Russian).
13. Sayadyan H., Nalbandyan A. and Khurshudyan G. 2005. Urban and peri-urban forestry and greening (UFG) -Yerevan case study. Report to FAO, FOWECA (Forestry outlook study for west and central Asia) study. 29P.
14. yerevan.am
15. Galstyan M.H., Mkrtchyan A.L. RA Natural Resources. *Teaching Guide for Higher Education Institution, Yerevan, ASAU, 2013, - 224 p.*
16. Harutyunyan L.V. *Armenian Nature, the Ways of its Conservation and Enrichment. Yerevan, Nahapet, 2005, 518 p. +136 p. colored insets.*
17. Harutyunyan V.S., Sargsyan K.Sh. *Teaching Guide for the Laboratory and Practical Classes in the Course of Environmental Monitoring, ASAU, Yerevan, 2012, 182 p.*
18. Melkumyan L.S., Galstyan M.H. *Basics of Nature Protection, Teaching Guide, Yerevan, "Zangak - 97", 2010, 312 p.*
19. Sayadyan H.Ya. *Vulnerability of Forest Ecosystems in Armenia and the Development of Greenhouse Absorbents "Climate Change Issues of Armenia" (Collection of Articles), 1999, - pp. 77-82.*
20. Harutyunyan L.V. *Landscaping of Yerevan Related to Some Peculiarities of the Microclimate // Bulletin of the Agricultural Sciences of the Armenian SSR. - 1960 - TXIII, N5, pp. 65-72.*
21. Vardanyan Zh.A., Grigoryan A.A. *Actual Problems of Landscaping in Yerevan // Mat. Int. Scientific. Conf. "Problems of Modern Dendrology", M., 2009, p. 431-433.*
22. Sargsyan K.Sh. *Green Ring of Yerevan. History of Establishment and Ways of Restoration. Yerevan, Asoghik, 2007, 160p.*